

INFLUENCE OF TOP MANAGEMENT COMMITMENT ON THE PERFORMANCE OF COUNTY SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN NAIROBI CITY, KENYA

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Abstract: The workplace in which organizations operate in the modern world is highly competitive and constantly changing. Strategic development and implementation should be one of the core activities of the organization in order to remain competitive and meet its objectives. Despite the increase in County Secondary schools in Nairobi, the performance of these schools is still deteriorating over the years. The Department of Education mandates all schools to develop and implement strategic plans. The main objective of the study therefore was to investigate the influence of top management support on the performance of County Secondary Schools in Nairobi City. The study population will be 57 County Secondary Schools in Nairobi City, and the research design will be descriptive. For data collection, self-administered questionnaires were used in the study. The observed data was then summarized and presented in the form of descriptive analyzes, including percentages, waves, methods, general deviations, and coefficients of variation, as well as frequency tables, pie charts, and bar graphs. The study concludes, based on the findings, that the support of senior management has a significant impact on the performance of high schools in the City of Nairobi, Kenya. The study recommended that the senior management team of all schools in Nairobi City, Kenya increase their commitment to implementing improved school performance improvement strategies..

Keywords: Top Management Support, School Performance.

1. INTRODUCTION

Learning can be defined as the process by which students acquire or expand their knowledge and skills. In contrast, performance can be characterized as the level at which the expressed objectives of gaining new abilities and information are accomplished. Formal schooling is impacted by a proper learning climate known as a school. This knowledge is influenced by professional staff known as teachers, and students are called students. Formal education programs aim to move students through a series of stages, including nursery, primary, secondary, and later, college and university. The school aims to prepare students to become adults and to be responsible members of society around the world. With this in mind, many countries make reading compulsory.

Various nations have different educational programs, yet they are additionally comparable in numerous ways. They all have stages where an understudy advances starting with one rudimentary level then onto the next, and one needs to finish one stage prior to continuing on to another. A common exam is usually administered at the end of each stage to assess the student's readiness to proceed to the next stage. These stages are generally classified as Primary, Secondary, and University education wherever one studies in the world. It is a key government responsibility all over the world to ensure that its citizens receive a quality education, leading to a prosperous society. The United Kingdom, Germany, Australia, and Canada have been recognized as academic achievements (May. 2014).

Nairobi County is the capital of Kenya, and there are 57 County Secondary schools. The population of each District School ranges from 400 to 1000 students, with three to six streams per school. National and regional schools are two

types of public high schools. District high schools are run by the District Government and are headed by principals who are assisted by the deputy principals who do the schoolwork. There are also teachers and administrators who contribute to school performance (M.O.E 2005)

The Kenyan government has recently increased its budget for education. Students now have access to free textbooks, and school resources have improved. The MOE now requires all public high schools to develop strategic plans, as stated in Session Paper No.1 of 2005. (MOE, 2005). As a result, High Schools are now producing annual strategic plans, but despite all government efforts, Nairobi District schools continue to produce results below the KCSE standard. (M.O.E 2012). As a result, there are concerns about the effectiveness of the strategic planning process and its implementation.

Organizational performance actually refers to the organization's ability to meet targeted strategies. According to Muchira (2013), organizational performance is the level at which a person meets the assumptions about how he or she should operate or continue in a particular position, position, appointment, or situation. Achieving goals and objectives has been used as a measure of organizational performance by Mahdani, Mohammed, Ali, and Ismael (2012). David (2005) described acting as a set of non-financial and financial indicators based on both direct and objective sources.

According to the context of High School Schools, performance is not always measured by school income or income. Key factors used to assess school performance are student behavior, level of transition of students from high school to university, and school enrollment numbers. High student enrollment numbers, good academic marks, and student participation in after-school and sports activities in the area and nationally will all show that District High School is doing well. This study will use non-financial performance measurement performance measures, customer satisfaction, efficiency, compliance, and efficiency to ensure uniformity across all high school public schools in Nairobi County.

Statement of the Problem

The government has made significant investments in Nairobi City County Schools, including improved infrastructure, free textbooks, and qualified teachers. County Secondary schools in Nairobi City, on the other hand, have been performing below average, with C-level points (MOE, 2017). Table 1.1 shows the intermediate performance of District Secondary Schools.

Table 1: Performance of County Secondary School in Nairobi.

Year	Mean Score	Mean Grade
2017	40.26	D+
2016	40.77	D+
2015	40.14	D+
2014	39.17	D
2013	39.98	D

The poor performance of County Secondary schools compared to Private Secondary Schools means that the utilization of a negative vital technique, prompting the school neglecting to meet the put forth objectives and goals. Lewa, Mutuku, and Mutuku (2009) Strathmore School, Sunshine Secondary School, Kianda School, and Loreto Convent performed continuously well, with average marks between B and B +. However, in the 2017 national examinations, schools such as Dandora and Kamkunji Secondary School received average C-marks (MOE, 2017).

It is common knowledge that the embraced key plans have not adequately executed the school's multiyear planning cycles (Lewa, Mutuku and Mutuku, 2009). Most state-funded schools fail to meet their objectives and targets, as evidenced by poor academic performance attributed to difficulties wreaking havoc on key plans (Ngware & Kosimbei, 2006). As a result, the purpose of this research is to determine the impact of strategy implementation on the performance of County Secondary Schools in Nairobi City.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Theoretical Literature Review

In theory, organizational assets are essential for a company to make a profit and perform well (Barney 2002). According to Ruler (2007), assets owned and operated by organizations can provide aggressive returns, leading to higher performance. Resources can be identified, such as utilities, finances, land, and PCs, or intangibles, such as staff verification, frustration, and licenses (Mayer & Solomon, 2006).

The strength of an association is its capacity to incorporate assets, individuals, and cycles into changing contributions to yields. Makadok (2001) characterizes abilities as particular sorts of administrations, for example, development and extra

client support, implanted and non-adaptable and attempting to work on the efficiency of other firm assets. Vital execution ought to be founded on the mix of the association's assets all the more proficiently and all in all such that improves the general presentation of the association. In principle, care and assurance during asset allotment can work on authoritative execution (Crook, Ketchen, Combs & Todd, 2008).

This theory was significant in this study since it made sense of the job of inside asset allotment in deciding the exhibition of an IHL association. While assets were efficiently designated to key hierarchical capabilities, authoritative execution improved, as did the institutional competitive advantage.

Empirical Literature Review

The most difficult aspect of performing a process is the organization's high responsibility for the key that you carry. This, in fact, is a prerequisite for the implementation of the procedure. Senior executives may from time to time show reluctance to provide urgency and commitment to killing strategies. This apparent unemployment continues to be a bad omen for all concerned (Rapa and Kauffman, 2005). In any case, it is reasonable to assume that the most common perceived issues of a specific wrong structure and lack of top organizational support are the limiting factors in the use of the effective framework (Aaltonen and Ikvalko, 2002). Aaltonen and Ikvalko explore the role of focused managers, arguing that they are "the main characters on the screen" who "play a key role in important books" (Aaltonen and Ikvalko, 2002). Meanwhile, Bartlett and Goshal (2006) define rooted directors as understaffed and whose role should be shifted to that of "guidance," building skills, providing assistance, and leading through leadership structures. Therefore, if they are not committed to performing their duties, lower levels of staff will not be equipped with assistance and courses with the help of good qualities. Regardless of the past, another obstacle to the use of productive approaches that has been widely considered to be the impact of the current organizational control (Langfield-Smith, 2007), especially its strategic structures (Marginson, 2002). In order to increase the likelihood that this approach will be implemented effectively, senior executives must demonstrate that low-level chairpersons have a common view of its structure and function, with its subtle basis, and its stress. Or maybe they should see an obvious backsliding. They should not put in any additional pressure to influence the views of employees (Rapa and Kauffman, 2005).

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study population will be 57 County Secondary Schools in Nairobi City, and the research design will be descriptive. For data collection, self-administered questionnaires were used in the study. The observed data was then summarized and presented in the form of descriptive analysis, which included percentages, frequencies, means, standard deviations, and coefficients of variation, as well as frequency tables, pie charts, and bar graphs.

4. FINDINGS

Table 2 shows the descriptive results for top management commitment.

Table 2: Top Management Commitment

	M	SD
Top management has an impact on the performance of Nairobi County Secondary Schools..	4.21	0.79
The commitment of top management strategically direction is an important factor in the performance of Nairobi High Schools.	3.64	1.36
For the project to succeed, top management should show their willingness to give strength and loyalty in the launch system.	4.01	0.99
Managers go to great lengths to persuade staff that their ideas strategy launch sounds..	4.56	0.44
The main impediment to strategy implementation is a lack of top management support..	4.74	0.16
Inability of managers to commit to their roles Encouragement of entrepreneurial characteristics results in employees lacking support and guidance.	3.84	1.16

The respondents strongly agreed that the main impediment to strategy implementation is a lack of top management support (M=4.74, SD=0.16), and that managers go to great lengths to persuade employees that their ideas for strategy implementation are effective (M=4.56, SD=0.44). Also, the respondents agreed that top management influences the performance of County Secondary Schools in Nairobi (M=4.21, SD=0.79), that top leaders should show their readiness to give energy and faithfulness to the execution interaction for the venture to succeed (M=4.01, SD=0.99), that when a company takes a customer-centric approach, it shows in every interaction (M=3.84, SD=1.16), and that managers' commitment to performing their roles is lacking (M=3.84, SD=1.16). Encouragement of entrepreneurial attributes leads to employees lacking support and guidance (M=3.64, SD=1.36). The findings are related to the Karanja, Kahuthia, and Muraguri (2020) study, which investigated the impact of senior management commitment on the performance of church-owned primary schools in Kiambu County, Kenya, and found that the senior management team empowered their employees to improve their performance.

Results of Regression Analysis

Table 3: Model Summary of Regression Analysis

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.434 ^a	.789	.772	1.416

Source: Research Data (2022)

The coefficient of correlation was 0.772, as shown in Table 3. This means that top management commitment explains approximately 77.2 percent of variations (R² = 0.772) in county secondary school performance in Nairobi City, Kenya, with the remaining 22.8 percent explained by factors not included in the model.

Coefficient of Determination of the Variable

Table 4: Coefficient of Determination of the Variable

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.704	0.271		2.597	.000
	Top management commitment	.552	.090	.405	6.133	.000

Table 4 shows the beta coefficients: top management commitment, 1 = 0.552 (t = 6.133, p 0.05). The coefficients are statistically significant (p 0.05). Thus, the equation predicting the influence of top management commitment components on school performance took the following form:

$$Y = 0.704 + 0.552X_1$$

Where Y = Performance and X₁ = Top management commitment

The regression model also revealed two implications: first, holding the top management commitment at zero, the performance of county secondary schools in Nairobi City, Kenya would be 0.704 units; second, a unit change in top management commitment results in a 0.552 change in the school performance.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The study concludes, based on the findings, that senior management support has a significant impact on the performance of high schools in the City of Nairobi, Kenya. The commitment of senior management enables school principals to empower their teachers to improve their performance, as well as to train and reward teachers for their achievements. The commitment of senior management also fosters relationships between school staff.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS

The study recommended that the senior management team of all schools in the City of Nairobi, Kenya increase their commitment to implementing established strategies to improve school performance. The senior management groups of these establishments ought to be exceptionally dedicated to settling on informed choices that will assist them with accomplishing their objectives and goals.

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